

Jatrocurin, a New Tetracyclic Triterpene from *Jatropha curcas*[†]

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From the stem of *Jatropha curcas* Linn. (fam. Euphorbiaceae) were isolated scopoletin methyl ether, friedelin, *epi*-friedelinol and a new tetracyclic triterpene ester designated jatrocurin which was shown to be 4 β -demethyl-24-methylenecycloartanyl 3 β -*p*-hydroxy-*m*-methoxy-*trans*-cinnamate (1) from spectral and chemical evidence.

Recently, we reported the structural elucidation of eight new diterpene lactones^{3,4} isolated from an Euphorbiaceae plant. Our continued search for new phytochemicals has resulted in the isolation of a new tetracyclic triterpenoid designated jatrocurin along with friedelin, *epi*-friedelinol and scopoletin methyl ether from another Euphorbiaceae plant *Jatropha curcas*, collected from West Bengal. Various parts of the plant find uses as folk medicine⁵; seeds and fruits are anthelmintic and used in chronic

dysentery; the plant sap is used in toothache etc. Jatrocurin was shown to have the structure 1 from the spectral and chemical evidence.

Results and Discussion

The petrol extract of the stems of *Jatropha curcas* afforded by silica gel column chromatography (cc) jatrocurin (1; 0.007%), m.p. 182 $^{\circ}$, C₄₀H₅₈O₄ (M^+ at m/z 602), $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 45^{\circ}$ (CHCl₃). The presence of a 3,4-dihydroxy-*trans*-cinnamoyl moiety⁶ in 1 was indicated by its spectral data: λ_{max} (EtOH) (log ϵ) 219 (4.27), 237 (4.20), 296–299(sh) (4.25), 329 nm (4.41); large alkali induced bathochromic shifts, λ_{max} (EtOH–0.1 M NaOH) (log ϵ) 218 (4.27), 243–244(sh) (4.20), 383 nm (4.63); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 533 (OH), 1 705 (ester C=O), 1 670 (conjugated C=O), 1 280 (ester O–CO), 1 022 (cyclopropane), 980 (*trans* –CH=CH–) and 815 cm⁻¹ (1,2,4-trisubstituted benzene).

The ¹H nmr spectrum (300 MHz; CDCl₃) of 1 confirmed the presence of the above moiety and provided additional structural information. Thus it showed the presence of a pair of downfield *trans*-olefinic protons (δ 7.60 and 6.27, 1H, d each, J 16 Hz), a trisubstituted aromatic ring with the following proton pattern: a pair of *ortho*-coupled protons—the more downfield one being further split

[†]Part 31 of the series 'Terpenoids and Related Compounds'. For Part 30 see Ref. 1 and for Part 29 see Ref. 2.

by a *meta*-proton (δ 7.06, 1H, dd, J 8.4 and 2 Hz; 6.90 (1H, d, J 8.4 Hz); one *meta*-coupled proton at δ 7.03 (1H, d, J 2 Hz), one phenolic hydroxyl proton at δ 5.97 (exchangeable with D_2O) and a methoxyl at δ 3.90 (3H, s). The above signals and the uv characteristics demonstrated the presence of a 4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxy-*trans*-cinnamoyl moiety. The presence of a phenolic OH group was confirmed by the formation of jatrorucin acetate (2), $C_{42}H_{60}O_5$ and jatrorucin monomethyl ether (3), m.p. 121° . The linking of the ester function at C-3 was evident from the appearance of H-3 of 1 at δ 4.64 (1H, m), its high $W_{1/2}$ value indicating its axial orientation and hence the equatorial orientation of the ester group. This was also supported by its ^{13}C spectral study. The nature of the triterpene alcohol part containing four secondary methyls, two tertiary methyls, one olefinic methylene and one cyclopropane methylene was revealed by the other 1H nmr signals : δ 0.17 and 0.42 (each 1H, d, J 3.9 Hz, methylene protons of a tetrasubstituted cyclopropane as in cycloartanol derivatives⁷), 4.66 and 4.71 [each 1H, br s, terminal olefinic methylene protons (ir band at 878 cm^{-1}), the former signal rising above the unresolved multiplet due to the ester methine proton at C-3], 1.03 (6H, d, J 6 Hz, two secondary CH_3 's at C-25), 0.89 and 0.90 (each 3H, d, J 6 Hz, $4\alpha\text{-}CH_3$, $20\alpha\text{-}CH_3$), 0.91 and 0.98 (each 3H, s, two tertiary methyls).

The electron-impact mass spectrum of 1 which is fully in conformity with the assigned structure, showed a very low intensity molecular ion peak at m/z 602. The mass spectral fragmentation (Chart 1) gave rise to characteristic peaks at m/z 408 and 194 assignable to ions *a* and *b* formed by McLafferty rearrangement as shown. The ion *a* underwent the cleavage of the most sterically strained ring-C by 1,5 H-transfer⁸, as shown, to give rise to ion *c* (m/z 160). Loss of three methyls and two hydrogen atoms from the fragment with ring-D gave rise to a strong ion *d* at m/z 201. The ion *b* underwent loss of elements of water to form the ion *e* responsible for the base peak at m/z 176. Formation of the ion fragment *g* (m/z 175)

Chart 1

was induced by the rupture of the cyclopropane ring followed by 1,2 and 1,5 H-transfers⁹ and loss of the side-chain (Chart 1).

Structure 1 for jatrorucin was confirmed by its alkaline hydrolysis to an aromatic acid and a neutral compound. The acid, $C_{10}H_{10}O_4$, m.p. 167° , was shown to be identical in all respects with an authentic sample of ferulic acid (4-hydroxy-3-methoxy-*trans*-cinnamic acid)¹⁰. The non-aromatic neutral hydrolysate, $C_{30}H_{50}O$ (M^+ 426), m.p. 132° , $[\alpha]_D + 38^\circ$

(CHCl₃), formed a monoacetyl derivative, C₃₂H₅₂O₂ (*M*⁺ 468), m.p. 109°, [α]_D + 56° (CHCl₃). The alcohol on oxidation with Jones's reagent gave the corresponding ketone, C₃₀H₄₈O (*M*⁺ 424), m.p. 84°. The physical and the spectral data of these three compounds compared well with those of cycloeucalenol (4), its acetate (5) and cycloeucalenone¹¹ (6) respectively, indicating identity in each case, although direct comparison could not be made due to non-availability of authentic samples.

The final confirmation of the structure 1 for jatrocurin and the manner of linking of its fragments were obtained from ¹³C nmr spectral study. The degree of protonation of each carbon atom was determined by APT experiments, and the carbon chemical shifts of the triterpene part were assigned by comparison with the δ_C values of cycloeucalenol (4) and cycloartanol¹² (7), taking into consideration simple additive rules, change of functional groups at C-3 and presence of a β-CH₃ group at C-4 in 7 (Table 1).

The structure and stereochemistry of the triterpenoid part of 1 also received confirmation from the fact that the δ_C values of all carbon atoms excepting C-23, C-24, C-25 and C-29 of 1 and 4 were very close to those of the corresponding carbons of cycloartanol (7). The olefinic C-24 and the allylic C-23 and C-25 underwent expected deshielding in 1 and 4 compared to 7 while C-29 in the former compounds appeared at an expected high field due to the absence of deshielding caused by C-30 (β-effect) as is present in 7. The chemical shift value (δ 14.4) indicates it to be the equatorial α-methyl (C-29).

The chemical shifts of the *trans*-cinnamoyl moiety of the triterpene 1 are comparable with those of the 3',4'-dihydroxy-*trans*-cinnamoyl residue of querspicatin-A [≡ 3β-(3',4'-dihydroxy-*trans*-cinnamoyloxy)-9α-hydroxy-7-oxo-lup-20(30)-ene]² (8), the difference being due to the replacement of the methoxy group at C-3' of 1 by a hydroxy group in the latter (Table 2). The structure of jatrocurin is thus established as 4β-demethyl-24-

methylenecycloartanyl 3β-*p*-hydroxy-*m*-methoxy-*trans*-cinnamate (1).

TABLE 1—CARBON CHEMICAL SHIFTS* OF JATROCURIN (1) (TRITERPENE PART), CYCLOEUCALENOL (4) AND CYCLOARTANOL (7)

Carbon	1 ^a	4 ^a	4 ^b	7 ^b
1	31.4	30.9	30.7	31.9
2	30.6	34.0	34.8	30.3
3	78.7	77.2	76.3	78.5
4	41.8	44.8	44.5	40.3
5	43.5	43.5	43.2	47.0
6	24.7	24.7	24.6	21.0
7	28.0	28.1	28.0	28.0
8	46.8	46.8	46.7	47.8
9	23.8	23.7	23.5	20.0
10	29.5	29.7	29.5	26.0
11	25.0	25.2	25.1	26.0
12	35.4	35.4	35.2	35.5
13	45.4	45.5	45.2	45.1
14	49.0	49.0	48.7	48.7
15	32.9	33.0	32.8	32.8
16	27.1	27.1	26.9	26.5
17	52.3	52.3	52.0	52.2
18	17.7 ^c	17.7 ^c	17.7 ^c	17.9 ^c
19	27.1	27.1	26.9	29.8
20	36.1	36.2	36.0	36.0
21	18.4 ^c	18.4 ^c	18.3 ^c	18.3 ^c
22	35.2	35.3	35.0	36.4
23	31.1	31.4	31.3	24.0
24	156.8	156.9	156.2	39.4
25	33.9	34.9	33.7	28.0
26	21.9	21.9	21.8	22.5
27	22.0	22.0	21.8	22.7
28	19.9 ^c	19.2 ^c	19.1 ^c	19.3 ^c
29	14.4	14.4	14.4	25.4
30	—	—	—	15.1
31	106.0	106.1	105.6	—

*Values are in ppm downfield from TMS used as an internal standard in CDCl₃ solution; δ(CDCl₃) = 76.9 ppm.

^aMeasured in Bruker AM 300L FT spectrometer at 75.0 MHz. ^bMeasured in Bruker HX 90E FT spectrometer at 22.63 MHz. ^cAssignments in the same column may be interchanged although those given here are preferred.

Scopoletin methyl ether¹³ (≡ 6,7-dimethoxycoumarin), friedelin¹⁴ and *epi*-friedelinol¹⁵ were isolated from other fractions of the silica gel cc of the petrol extract of the plant material.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra were measured in KBr pellets and uv spectra in 95% aldehyde-free

TABLE 2 - ^{13}C NMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF THE ESTER MOIETIES OF JATROCURIN (1) AND QUERSPICATIN-A² (8)

Compd no.	C-1'	C-2'	C-3'	C-4'	C-5'	C-6'	C-7'	C-8'	C-9'
1	127.3	109.6	148.0	146.9	114.8	122.8	144.3	116.3	167.0
8	127.5	115.5	146.3	146.9	116.1	122.4	145.4	116.2	167.2

ethanol. ^1H nmr spectra were run at 300 MHz and ^{13}C nmr at 75 MHz, both in CDCl_3 using TMS as the internal standard. Ms were recorded in a mass spectrometer having a direct inlet system and operating at 70 eV; figures within parenthesis after m/z values represent relative intensities of peaks. For column chromatography silica gel (60–120 mesh) was used; tlc : microscopic slides coated with silica gel G; fractions with similar tlc behaviour were combined; spots were visualised in uv-light and on exposure to I_2 vapour. Petrol used had b.p. 60–80°. Analytical samples were routinely dried over P_2O_5 for 24 h under reduced pressure. Anhydrous Na_2SO_4 was used for drying organic solvents. The plant material was collected in the neighbourhood of Calcutta.

Extraction : Air-dried and powdered stems of *J. curcas* Linn. (1 kg) was extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with petrol and CHCl_3 successively for 40 h each. The extracts were concentrated under reduced pressure and separately chromatographed over silica gel, elution being carried out with solvents and solvent mixtures of increasing polarity.

Isolation of friedelin and epi-friedelinol : The concentrate of the petrol extract was chromatographed over silica gel (60–120 mesh). The combined petrol-EtOAc (99 : 1) eluate showing two spots in tlc was concentrated under reduced pressure to afford a solid residue. The latter upon repeated cc over silica gel followed by crystallisation from CHCl_3 -petrol (b.p. 40–60°) afforded friedelin (8 mg), m.p. 256°, R_f 0.6, CHCl_3 -MeOH (99 : 1), ν_{max} 2 910, 2 826, 1 712 (C=O), 1 457, 1 387 cm^{-1} and epi-friedelinol (10 mg), m.p. 278°, R_f 0.5, CHCl_3 -MeOH (99 : 1), ν_{max} 3 460 (OH), 2 940, 2 830, 1 440 (C-H bending) 1 375 (*gem*-dimethyl), 1 350 cm^{-1} . The identity of each was established by direct comparison (m.m.p.—no depression, superposable ir) with authentic samples available in the laboratory.

Isolation of jatrorcurin (1) : The white solid obtained from the combined petrol-EtOAc (19 : 1) eluate showing one major and another minor spots in tlc was subjected to repeated column chromatography (cc) over silica gel, followed by crystallisation from CHCl_3 -petrol to afford colourless needle-shaped crystals of jatrorcurin (1; 70 mg), m.p. 182°, R_f 0.25, MeOH- CHCl_3 (1 : 99), $[\alpha]_D + 45.3^\circ$ (CHCl_3 , c 0.07) (Found : C, 79.52; H, 9.84. $\text{C}_{40}\text{H}_{58}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 79.73; H, 9.63%); it showed greenish colouration with neutral FeCl_3 solution; ν_{max} 3533 (OH), 1 705 (ester C=O), 1 670 (conjugated C=O), 1 635, 1 605, 1 520, 1 465, 1 450, 1 430, 1 380, 1 280 (ester O-CO), 1 160, 1 120, 1 022 (cyclopropane), 988, 972, 878 (C=CH₂), 815 cm^{-1} (1,2,4-trisubstituted benzene); ^1H nmr spectral characteristics and their assignments have already been discussed; ms (EI) m/z (rel. int.) 602 (M^+) (0.5), 603 ($M^+ + 1$) (0.3), 604 ($M^+ + 2$) (0.2), 408 (ion *a*) (13.2), 394 (10.4), 393 (9.7), 201 (*d*) (23.5), 200 (6.4), 194 (*b*) (10.6), 193 (*b*-H) (43.2), 192 (193-H) (36.7), 188 (14.9), 187 (17.4), 176 (*e*) (100), 175 (*g*)⁸ (94), 160 (*c*) (23.9) and many ion fragments related to *c* or produced by the cleavage of the side chain : m/z 145 (35.4), 144 (48.3), 143 (44.0), 134 (30.6), 132 (28.5), 120 (33.7), 118 (34.5), 108 (47.8), 107 (69.7), 106 (51.3), 104 (41.1), 95 (54.9), 94 (62.5), 83 (21.0), 81 (54.1), 69 (42.9), 55 (75.7), 43 (51.0), 41 (42.6).

Isolation of scopoletin methyl ether (\cong 6,7-dimethoxycoumarin) : The petrol-EtOAc (4 : 1) eluate from silica gel cc afforded a solid residue, which upon repeated cc over silica gel followed by crystallisation from CHCl_3 -petrol (b.p. 40–60°) furnished scopoletin methyl ether in pale yellow crystalline needles (10 mg), m.p. 142°, R_f 0.5, CHCl_3 -MeOH (95 : 5); ν_{max} 1 722, 1 619, 1 557, 1 517 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 7.63 and 6.28 (each 1H, d, J 9.6 Hz, H-4 and H-3 protons), 6.87 (1H, s, H-8), 6.81

(1H, s, H-5), 3.95 (3H, s, OCH₃) 3.92 (3H, s, OCH₃). The identity was confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample.

Jatrocurin acetate (2) : Solution of jatrocurein (1; 15 mg) in pyridine (0.31 ml) was treated (24 h, room temperature) with Ac₂O (0.40 ml). Extractive work-up followed by silica gel cc and crystallisation from CHCl₃-MeOH afforded the acetate in fine colourless needles (8 mg), m.p. 172° (Found : C, 77.94; H, 9.15. C₄₂H₆₀O₅ requires : C, 78.26; H, 9.32%); ν_{\max} 3 020 (cyclopropane), 1 762 (phenolic acetate C=O), 1 717 (ester C=O), 1 639, 1 602, 1 514, 1 467, 1 422, 1 374, 1 337, 1 279 (ester O-CO), 1 262, 1 177, 1 159, 1 124, 1 037 (cyclopropane), 992, 887, (C=CH₂), 818 cm⁻¹ (1,2,4-trisubstituted benzene); ¹H nmr δ 0.18 and 0.43 (each 1H, d, *J* 3.9 Hz cyclopropane methylene protons), 0.89 (3H, d, *J* 6.3 Hz, CHCH₃), 0.90 (3H, d, *J* 6.3 Hz, CHCH₃), 0.92 and 0.98 (each 3H, s, two t-CH₃'s), 1.03 (6H, d, *J* 6.9 Hz, two CHCH₃'s at C-25), 2.32 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 3.86 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.65 (1H, s, H-3), 4.68 and 4.71 (each 1H, br s, terminal methylene protons), 6.38 and 7.63 (each 1H, d, *J* 15.9 Hz, *trans*-olefinic protons), 7.04 (1H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz, H-5'), 7.11 (1H, s, H-2'), 7.12 (1H, dd, *J* 8.1 and 1.5 Hz, H-6'); ms (EI) *m/z* (rel. int.) 644 (*M*⁺) (0.2), 643 (*M*⁺-1) (0.5), 642 (643-1) (0.5), 408 (*a*) (12.8), 394 (4.0), 393 (11.9), 236 (*b*') (5.4), 201 (*d*) (5.9), 200 (9.0), 193 (*b*'-COCH₃), 192 (35.2), 188 (17.5), 187 (14.6), 176 (*e*) (12.6), 175 (*g*) (100), 160 (*c*) (26.9), 144 (53.5), 143 (44.5), 134 (37.4), 132 (37.3), 120 (43.2), 118 (40.2), 108 (69.4), 107 (68.3), 106 (62.7), 104 (51.5), 95 (70.9), 94 (71.7), 83 (23.7), 81 (54.3), 69 (51.3), 55 (64.2), 43 (62.3), 41 (39.4).

Jatrocurin methyl ether (3) : To a solution of jatrocurein (10 mg) in dry acetone, methyl iodide (2 ml) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (0.2 g) were added and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h, then cooled and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated to yield a light yellow residue which upon chromatography afforded from the petrol-ethyl acetate (99 : 1) eluate jatrocurein methyl ether (3), crystallising from CHCl₃-petrol as light yellow needles (6 mg),

m.p. 121°; ν_{\max} 1 705 (ester C=O), 1 628, 1 595, 1 578, 1 515, 1 465, 1 305, 1 265 (ester O-CO), 1 175, 1 160, 1 140, 1 025 (cyclopropane), 985, 885, 845, 800 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ 0.17 and 0.42 (each 1H, d, *J* 3.9 Hz and 3.6 Hz, cyclopropane methylene protons), 0.89 (3H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz, CHCH₃), 0.90 (3H, d, *J*, 6.3 Hz, CHCH₃), 0.91 and 0.97 (each 3H, s, two t-CH₃'s), 1.02 and 1.03 (each 3H, d, *J* 6.9 Hz and 6.6 Hz, two CHCH₃ at C-25), 3.91 (6H, s, two OCH₃), 4.65 (1H, s, H-3), 4.65 and 4.70 (each 1H, br s, terminal methylene protons), 6.32 and 7.62 (each 1H, d, *J* 15.9 Hz, *trans*-olefinic protons), 6.85 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, H-5'), 7.05 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz, H-2'), 7.10 (1H, dd, *J* 8.1 and 1.5 Hz, H-6').

Alkaline hydrolysis of jatrocurein (1). *Formation of cycloeucalenol* (4) : A solution (9 ml) of jatrocurein (1; 36 mg) in 5% aqueous KOH-MeOH was refluxed on a steam-bath for 8.5 h (the progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc at 1 h intervals). After removal of MeOH under reduced pressure, the reaction mixture was diluted with H₂O (50 ml), extracted with CHCl₃, washed with H₂O, dried and the solvent evaporated. The residue was chromatographed and crystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH to afford cycloeucalenol (4; 20 mg) as needles, m.p. 132°, (*M*⁺ at *m/z* 426), [α]_D + 38.07° (CHCl₃, *c* 0.07) (Found : C, 84.27; H, 11.55. C₃₀H₅₀O requires : C 84.51; H, 11.74%); it gave positive Liebermann-Burchardt test producing deep brown colour with green fluorescence and gave light yellow colour with TNM; ν_{\max} 3 020 (cyclopropane), 3 302 (OH), 2 932, 2 912, 2 832, 1 637, 1452, 1372, 1 105, 1 042, 1 020, 880 cm⁻¹ (C=CH₂); ¹H nmr δ 4.71 and 4.66 (each 1H, br s, terminal methylene protons), 3.21 (m, *W*_{1/2} 15 Hz CHOH), 0.42 and 0.17 (each 1H, d, *J* 3.9 Hz, cyclopropane methylene protons), 1.03 (3H, d, *J* 6.9 Hz CHCH₃), 1.02 (3H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz, CHCH₃), 0.98 (3H, d, *J* 6 Hz, CHCH₃), 0.90 (3H, d, *J* 6.3 Hz, CHCH₃), 0.97 (3H, s, t-CH₃), 0.89 (3H, s, t-CH₃); ms (EI) *m/z* (rel. int.) 426 (*M*⁺) (2.5), 411 (*M*⁺-CH₃) (5.8), 408 (*a*) (11.3), 394 (11.1), 393 (14.8), 300 (*f*) (9.0), 201 (*d*) (4.6), 200 (15.7), 188 (16.9), 187

(11.8), 175 (g) (8.6), 173 (28.6), 160 (c) (33.0), 159 (26.6), 146 (44.0), 145 (35.4), 134 (37.8), 132 (44.4), 120 (49.1), 118 (43.7), 108 (51.8), 106 (65.6), 104 (58.6), 95 (76.8), 94 (71.4), 83 (34.4), 82 (32.1), 81 (64.8), 69 (66.1), 55 (100), 43 (49.5), 41 (78.0).

Ferulic acid : The aqueous part was neutralised with 2M HCl and evaporated. The addition of MeOH and evaporation was repeated thrice. The residue was crystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH to give ferulic acid (\equiv 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy-*trans*-cinnamic acid), m.p. 167° (lit. 168°). The identity was confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample.

Cycloeucalenyl acetate (5) : A solution of cyclo-eucalenol (4; 8 mg) in pyridine (0.25 ml) was treated (20 h, room temperature) with Ac₂O (0.35 ml). The mixture was poured into ice-cold 1M HCl and extracted with ice-cold CHCl₃. The residue obtained after evaporation was crystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH as fine colourless needles (5; 3 mg), m.p. 109° (lit. 110°); ν_{\max} 3 025 (cyclopropane), 2 915, 2 830, 1 735 (acetate C=O), 1 640, 1 460, 1 380, 1 250, 1 105, 1 040, 1 025, 885 (C=CH₂) and 810 cm⁻¹.

Cycloeucalenone (6) : To a solution of 4 (10 mg) in acetone (2 ml), freshly prepared Jones's reagent (5 ml) was added at 0° with constant stirring. After 2 h the mixture was diluted with H₂O and extracted with CHCl₃. The organic layer was washed with H₂O, dried and evaporated. The resulting residue (12 mg) was purified by chromatography to give cycloeucalenone (6), crystallising from CHCl₃-MeOH as colourless needles, m.p. 84°; ν_{\max} 1 715 (C=O), 1 640, 1 460, 1 450, 1 375, 1 260, 1 100, 1 020, 880 (C=CH₂), 880 cm⁻¹.

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